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Two concepts of quality in non-traditional research fields: the case of creative arts¹

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Introduction

Research quality criteria – and the underlying concepts of what is good and bad research – are the foundation of science evaluation systems. Social researchers have demonstrated that the conceptions of quality and excellence differ between research fields and disciplines (e.g. Hug and Ochsner 2022; Reymert et al. 2020). Less attention has been paid to the coexistence of different and potentially competing concepts of value within a single discipline. While prominent sociological theories highlight the plurality of concepts of worth within particular domains (Boltanski and Thevenot 2006), few studies have used those theories to investigate diverse notions of value within research disciplines.

This paper explores different conceptions of quality in a non-traditional research field – the field of Art (including artistic disciplines such as visual and performing arts). Specifically, we focus on the underlying concepts of quality in the evaluation of the arts within performance-based research funding systems – PRFS (Hicks 2012). We call the Art a ‘non-traditional research field’ as it has traditionally been located beyond the context of university research and specialises in the production of non-traditional research outputs (NTROs) – outputs that do not take the form of typical research publications but comprise different forms of creative expression such as musical compositions, dance performances, photographic exhibitions, creative written works, etc.

The field of Art operates at the intersection of academic research and professional practice. Academics in this field are usually active professionals in the arts sector, employed within the academy because of their professional expertise. The Arts is one of the primary domains of practice-based research – a form of research where knowledge is gained by means of practice and the outcomes of that practice (Vear 2022). Therefore, evaluation of outputs in the Arts is linked with concepts of value pertaining to two different social contexts: that of the professional arts sector and that of the Academy. The aim of this research is to investigate those concepts and understand how different perceptions of worth coexist within a single research field.

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Methods

The primary data for this research are 90 interviews with Polish artist-academics and art colleges' management and administrators responsible for research evaluation. Two waves of interviews were conducted. The first wave included 60 open-ended interviews and examined the effects of the evaluation systems on art schools and their employees; the second wave (N=30) was based on structured interviews using a questionnaire and investigated the conceptions of quality in artistic disciplines. This article mostly presents the results of the second wave; findings from open-ended interviews will be used in further analysis to understand and interpret the results of the questionnaire.

The design of the questionnaire used in the second wave of interviews drew on earlier stages of the current research project (2019/35/D/HS5/00009), which included a qualitative comparative analysis of ten PRFSs (in Australia, the Czech Republic, Italy, Lithuania, New Zealand, Poland, Portugal, Slovakia, Spain, the United Kingdom) (Lewandowska, Kulczycki & Ochsner, forthcoming). We identified criteria used in those PRFSs to evaluate non-traditional research outputs in artistic disciplines. In this paper, we focus on higher order principles of evaluation – using those criteria, our goal is to understand the underlying concepts of quality guiding PRFS evaluations.

During interviews, the respondents were asked to complete the questionnaire by rating the importance of each criterion for judging the quality of artistic outputs on a 5-point Likert-type scale. In addition, respondents were asked to explain how they understood the criteria and to justify their ratings. This mixed-method approach (a questionnaire and an interview) was applied because the criteria drawn from evaluation documents were quite generic and, to be able to draw meaningful conclusions, it was necessary to understand the subjective meanings our respondents attached to them. Table 1 lists the criteria and presents descriptive statistics.

Table 1. Quality criteria and descriptive statistics

Criteria	Mean	SD
Significance for research (C1)	3.07	1.17
Significance for artistic development (C2)	4.30	0.79
Contribution to knowledge/ understanding (C3)	4.00	0.87
Rigour (methodological) (C4)	2.33	1.09
Creative or intellectual context (references) (C5)	4.23	0.90
Originality: external (in relation to other works within the discipline) (C6)	3.83	0.87
Originality: internal (in relation to earlier versions of the output) (C7)	3.50	1.17
World-class level (the output ranks with the best within its discipline) (C8)	3.83	1.05
International exposure (dissemination) (C9)	3.57	1.04
Peer recognition (e.g. awards, festival invitations) (C10)	3.97	1.03
Scale of work (e.g. duration of a play, cast size) (C11)	2.13	1.11
Output type (e.g. a concert, a solo exhibition) (C12)	3.17	1.09

Results

We conducted an exploratory factor analysis to identify higher order concepts of value in artistic disciplines using the psych package in R. A parallel analysis and scree plot examination were applied to determine the number of factors; two overall factors were suggested. Maximum likelihood estimation was used with direct oblimin rotation because of

expected factor correlation. After testing all 12 criteria, one item split (C12) across several factors and two items (C7) did not load on any factor using the criterion that loadings must be greater than 0.3. Therefore, the criteria C12 (*Output type*) and C7 (*Originality: internal*) were eliminated from further analysis. Another 2-factor model was tested, and the factor loadings are presented in Table 2. This model achieved simple structure with each item loading on one and only one factor. The reliability of both factors were acceptable with 0.71 for Factor 1 and 0.76 for Factor 2 (Taber 2018).

Table 2. 2-Factor Model Loadings

Item	Factor 1	Factor 2
C1	0.96	-0.7
C2	0.50	0.30
C3	0.64	0.02
C4	0.41	0.11
C5	0.29	0.50
C6	-0.05	0.40
C8	-0.02	0.50
C9	-0.06	0.91
C10	-0.03	0.76
C11	0.14	0.48

Factor 1 included four items: *Significance for research* (C1), *Contribution to knowledge/ understanding* (C3), *Significance for artistic development* (C2), *Rigour* (C4). This factor includes criteria related to the cognitive dimension of outputs and their contribution to research and art and thus we labelled this higher order quality concept as ‘cognition and development’. Factor 2 included six items: *International exposure* (C9), *Peer recognition* (C10), *World-class level* (C8), *Creative or intellectual context* (C5), *Scale of work* (C11), *Originality: external* (C6). This factor includes criteria focused on the social context and reception as well as creative referents and conventions; thus, we label it ‘recognition and creative influence’. The mean scores for each factor were: Factor 1 M= 3.43 (SD=0.73), Factor 2 M=3.6 (SD= 0.67), which indicates that concepts were rated comparably in terms of importance.

Conclusion

Using quality criteria from ten country PRFSs, we identified two primary concepts of quality guiding PRFS evaluations in artistic disciplines (see Table 3). The first concept – ‘cognition and development’ – emphasizes the investigative and cognitive quality of outputs as well as artistic/research progress; thus, it refers to quality standards commonly used in academic research evaluation. The second quality concept – ‘recognition and creative influence’ – focuses on quality aspects that play a significant role in professional arts sector, such as validation from critics and peers as well as creative influences (creative references, originality) and formal aspects of artworks (scale of work).

Our analysis suggests that outputs in artistic disciplines are evaluated using two different (and potentially competing) quality standards that are mobilised to justify the value of outputs. Further qualitative analysis will be conducted to gain a deeper understanding of the meaning of those concepts, as well as how they overlap and coexist within the field of Art.

Table 3. Higher order concepts of quality in artistic disciplines

Concepts of quality	
‘Cognition and development’	‘Recognition and creative influence’
Significance for research	International exposure
Contribution to knowledge/ understanding	Peer recognition
Significance for artistic development	World-class level
Rigour	Creative or intellectual context
	Scale of work
	Originality: external

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